

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer Review Report For:

Uzoechina, B. I., Okeke, A. C., Ekwoh, G. A., Oladipo, A. O. (2025). Growth trajectory and informal sector businesses in Nigeria: the case of Enugu state. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(2), 2025. e2023-0546. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250201>

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Uzoechina, B. I., Okeke, A. C., Ekwoh, G. A., Oladipo, A. O. (2025). Peer review report for: Growth trajectory and informal sector businesses in Nigeria: the case of Enugu state. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(2), 2025. e2023-0546. Zenodo. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14031674>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

The reviewers did not authorize the disclosure of their identities.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

The reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Authors' responses

Comments from Reviewer 1:

1. *Update your literature with current citations: Thank you for this observation. Efforts have been made to update this with recent works. However, citations related to theories and methods were not altered.*

Comments from Reviewer 2:

1. *Provided adequate justifications for “area of study- Enugu: This has been provided and is also highlighted for easy identification. I am open for modification if the justification provided is still not sufficient.*
2. *Conduct more scientific review of recent literature to bring out the gaps in the literature: This has been attended to. Further reviews were done and contribution to knowledge highlighted. The works reviewed were also critiqued to bring out the gap in literature.*
3. *The authors are advised to seek assistance from an academician who is proficient in English: This has been done and the language has improved.*

From the general comments from the Editors

1. *Literature currency and the justification of your research should be worked on: Thank you for these observations. Serious efforts have been made to improve on this. These improvements have been highlighted.*
2. *Generally, the discussion should reflect sufficient details to that can inform both theoretical and policy perspectives for stakeholders in the regional informal context of the study: This has also been attended to.*
3. *Detailed explanations and possible implications are missing: The paper has been revised to include sufficient details and implications*

Thank you for your thorough review of this manuscript. I am willing to continue to improve on it for best outcome.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

The reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of their identity

Date review returned: 04-Apr-2024

Recommendation: Reject

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

Major Comments

1. *There are many categorical statements without any relevant support. This is grossly unacceptable. For example, the following sentences are stated in the introduction: “Though, the country has recorded periods of recessions in the last four decades as shown in the figure 1.1 below, the overall impressive performance of the economy appears not have engendered inclusive growth.” “Evidently, poverty and unemployment are rising in Nigeria. Nigeria depends on borrowing to finance her capital projects and sometimes her recurrent expenditure. This deficit financing has been sustained for more than two decades now”. These categorical statements do not have any*

support in the paper. Provide either relevant arguments, data, or statistics to support the categorical statements because from the graph alone, there is nothing to show that the “impressive performance of the economy appears not to have engendered inclusive growth”. The other categorical statements are also not supported. This is an academic paper – one cannot make categorical statements without support with relevant arguments, data, statistics, etc.

2. The introduction itself, as a whole, is too long. There are lots of irrelevant issues that do not belong in an introduction that have been presented. Introduce the topic, establish the need and motivation for the study, present the research questions and objectives, and the rationale for the study. An introduction should not be more than 2 double space pages. The figures and tables in the introduction are necessary. The objectives and research question(s) of the study are also not clearly stated or expressed in the study. Please clearly express the purpose of the study.

3. Literature Review: the review of extant literature in the paper is too cursory. Conduct a better review of literature.

4. Research design and method: There are a number of issues with the research design and method. First, present a sample of the questions included in the questionnaire used for the survey design. Second, how was the questionnaire distributed to the respondents? Third, in designing a new questionnaire, there is need for a pilot study to be conducted using a small sample, conducting the necessary tests through factor analysis to ensure that the questions actually measure what they are meant to measure, and the use of necessary tests to ensure the validity and reliability of the research instrument – there is no evidence from the description of the research process that these important steps have been adequately followed. Present the results of the factor analysis conducted after the pilot test and provide more details on how the pilot test was conducted.

5. Variables: What are the variables in the model of the study? This is not stated in anywhere in the paper. It is not enough to state an empirical model in equations. Please, explain what each of the elements in the equations represent and how one equation was derived from the other. Also explain how the variables were constructed from the survey data, and how they fit into the different elements of the equations.

6. The section titled “test for reliability” is not only confusing but unnecessary. First, the paper did not develop any hypothesis until in the presentation of results section. It is therefore surprising to see in this section that hypotheses were tested. Second, Cronbach Alpha is not used for hypothesis testing.

7. The hypotheses that were subsequently stated and tested in the results section were not properly developed. Hypotheses were also stated in the wrong section of the paper. The author(s) should develop the hypotheses properly and present them in the proper section within the paper.

8. Discussion of Findings: First, in discussing the findings, the author(s) should integrate the findings of the study with the findings of extant literature from within Africa and other contexts – this has not been done. Second, what are the limitations of the study? The author(s) should present the limitations of the study and make suggestions for future research. Third, what are the policy and practical implications for business of the findings of the study?

Other Comments

1. Provide proper citations for the data and statistics presented and used in the paper. The second paragraph in the introduction, for example, has data on population of Nigeria in two separate sentences and none of them has any citation (see the following sentences on lines 8-11: With a population estimated at 217,597,665,

Nigeria has a substantial and open economy. Nigeria is ranked seventh in the world with a population that makes up 2.64% of the global population.) Each of these two sentences should have proper citations on the source of the data and statistic. Indeed, many sentences in this paragraph lack proper citation.

2. Figure 1.1 is showing the source as authors' computation. Yes, the graph on economic growth in Nigeria was computed and derived by the author(s) but the data on economic growth in Nigeria used for the computation could not have been derived by the author(s). Please provide the source of the data used for constructing the graph.

3. Table 1 presents the informal sector size of some selected countries. The purpose of the table is well understood. However, there has to be a systematic means to which the countries being compared were selected. What is the basis of selecting the countries – the developed countries and the African countries selected should be selected based on a criterium. For example, for the African countries, are the author(s) selecting one African country from each of the regions in Africa, or the top African countries in respect of economic size, population size, or the African countries with the lowest (or highest) informal sector size? How exactly were the countries (both the developed countries and the African countries) selected to be compared?

4. Tables 4.1 to tables 4.6 s– The title of the tables give the impression that the data is for the population of the informal sector rather than for the sample used in the study. Please change the titles of the tables to reflect that it is for the sample and not for the population.

Reviewer 2 Report

The reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of their identity

Date review returned: 12-Apr-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author:

This study investigated the growth path of informal sector businesses after government support efforts, and the factors that sustain this growth trajectory in Enugu State, Nigeria. The topic is relevant and of interest to all developing and emerging countries because of the importance of informal businesses in job creation and poverty alleviation in these countries.

The manuscript refers to unorganised sector, unofficial sector, traditional sector, contemporary, conventional, modernized sector, and so forth. The title refers to informal sector, therefore I recommend that the author consistently refers to informal sector (and formal sector) throughout the document.

In the introduction the author mentions validating or invalidating the dual hypotheses, But the hypotheses is not stated in the introduction or within the literature review. I think it is important to state each hypothesis specifically before we get to the methodology and results.

The methodology is described well. There is some discrepancy about the sample size. The author states that the sample size of 384 was increased to 500 using purposive sampling. But then mentions that 520 questionnaires were distributed of which 500 were filled in correctly. However, Tables 4.1-4.6 indicate a total of 503 respondents. Please clarify. I am not an expert in terms of quantitative analysis, but the statistics seem to be in order.

The recommendations are exactly the same as the article in Journal of Economic Studies. As other factors were investigated in this study, there should be other recommendations that may be relevant. Or at least re-write or paraphrase, so as to not copy the exact wording from the other article.

Ensure that the use of 'et al' is consistently applied throughout the manuscript. Xia et al (2011) is not included in the References. The alphabetical order of the reference list is not correct, please check.

Large parts of the article are exactly the same as the article published in the Journal of Economic Studies. I think the journal should consider and confirm the level of self-plagiarism and what is acceptable for publication in this Journal.

The language in some instances is too informal and not academic. I recommend that the manuscript be language edited to improve the formal, scientific writing style. This may also assist to eliminate some of the similarities between this manuscript and the published article from Journal of Economic Studies.

Please see the attached file for more comments and track changes.

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